

Supplementary Materials:

Straight versus branched chain substituents in 4'-(butoxyphenyl)-3,2':6',3"-terpyridines: Effects on (4,4) coordination network assemblies

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Figure. S1. Electrospray mass spectrum of *rac-2*.

Figure. S2. Electrospray mass spectrum of **4**.

Figure. S3. ^1H NMR spectrum of compound *rac-2* (500 MHz, 298 K, CDCl_3). * = residual CHCl_3 .

Figure. S4. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of compound *rac-2* (126 MHz, 298 K, CDCl_3). * = CDCl_3 .

Figure. S5. HMQC spectrum of compound *rac-2* (^1H 500 MHz, ^{13}C 126 MHz, 298 K, CDCl_3). * = residual CHCl_3 or CDCl_3 .

Figure. S6. HMBC spectrum of compound *rac-2* (^1H 500 MHz, ^{13}C 126 MHz, 298 K, CDCl_3). * = residual CHCl_3 or CDCl_3 .

Figure. S7. ^1H NMR spectrum of compound **4** (500 MHz, 298 K, CDCl_3). * = residual CHCl_3 .

Figure. S8. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of compound **4** (126 MHz, 298 K, CDCl_3). * = CDCl_3 .

Figure. S9. HMQC spectrum of compound **4** (^1H 500 MHz, ^{13}C 126 MHz, 298 K, CDCl_3). * = residual CHCl_3 or CDCl_3 .

Figure. S10. HMBC spectrum of compound **4** (^1H 500 MHz, ^{13}C 126 MHz, 298 K, CDCl_3). * = residual CHCl_3 or CDCl_3 .

Figure. S11. ^1H NMR spectrum of compound **3a** (500 MHz, 298 K, CDCl_3). * = residual CHCl_3 .

Figure. S12. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of compound **3a** (126 MHz, 298 K, CDCl_3). * = CDCl_3 .

Figure. S13. HMQC spectrum of compound **3a** (^1H 500 MHz, ^{13}C 126 MHz, 298 K, CDCl_3). * = residual CHCl_3 or CDCl_3 .

Figure. S14. HMBC spectrum of compound **3a** (^1H 500 MHz, ^{13}C 126 MHz, 298 K, CDCl_3). * = residual CHCl_3 or CDCl_3 .

MS Spectrum
 Line#:1 R.Time:----(Scan#:----)
 MassPeaks:22
 Spectrum Mode:Averaged 0.000-0.133(0-17) Base Peak:684(2150057)
 BG Mode:Averaged 0.200-2.900(25-349) Segment 1 - Event 1

Figure. S15. Electrospray mass spectrum of compound **3a**.

MS Spectrum
Line#:1 R.Time:---(Scan#:---)
MassPeaks:10
Spectrum Mode:Averaged 0.000-0.150(0-19) Base Peak:382(3164565)
BG Mode:Averaged 0.167-2.933(21-353) Segment 1 - Event 1

Figure. S16. Electrospray mass spectrum of compound **3**.

Figure. S17. ¹H NMR spectrum of compound **3** (500 MHz, 298 K, CDCl₃). * = residual CHCl₃.

Figure. S18. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of compound **3** (126 MHz, 298 K, CDCl_3). * = CDCl_3 .

Figure. S19. HMQC spectrum of compound **3** (^1H 500 MHz, ^{13}C 126 MHz, 298 K, CDCl_3). * = residual CHCl_3 or CDCl_3 .

Figure. S20. HMBC spectrum of compound **3** (^1H 500 MHz, ^{13}C 126 MHz, 298 K, CDCl_3). * = residual CHCl_3 or CDCl_3 .

Figure. S21. The solid-state FT-IR spectrum of *rac*-**2**.

Figure. S22. The solid-state FT-IR spectrum of **3**.

Figure. S23. The solid-state FT-IR spectrum of **4**.

Figure. S24. The solid-state FT-IR spectrum of $[\{\text{Co}(\text{rac-2})_2(\text{NCS})_2\} \cdot \text{CHCl}_3]_n$.

Figure. S25. The solid-state FT-IR spectrum of $[\{\text{Co}(\mathbf{3})_2(\text{NCS})_2\}]_n$.

Figure. S26. The solid-state FT-IR spectrum of $[\{\text{Co}(\mathbf{4})_2(\text{NCS})_2\} \cdot \text{CHCl}_3]_n$.

Figure. S27. ORTEP representation of the coordination sphere of atom Co1 (with symmetry generated Co centers) in $[\{\text{Co}(\text{rac-}\mathbf{2})_2(\text{NCS})_2\} \cdot \text{CHCl}_3]_n$ (symmetry codes: i = $1-x, 1-y, 1-z$; ii = $1/2-x, -1/2+y, 1/2-z$; iii = $3/2-x, 1/2+y, 3/2-z$; iv = $1/2+x, 1/2-y, 1/2+z$; v = $1/2-x, 1/2+y, 1/2-z$).

Figure. S28. Overlays of parts of the (4,4) nets in $[\{\text{Co}(\textit{rac}\text{-}\mathbf{2})_2(\text{NCS})_2\}\cdot\text{CHCl}_3]_n$ (red) and $[\{\text{Co}(\mathbf{4})_2(\text{NCS})_2\}\cdot\text{CHCl}_3]_n$ (blue).